

Getting started on BlueSky

A guide for scientists

Last update: 15th Dec 2024

[An introduction to BlueSky & how it works](#)

[Tips](#)

[Finding people to follow](#)

[Find the people you were following](#)

[Find new people to follow - Starter packs](#)

[Feeds - follow timelines based on topics of interest](#)

[Privacy settings](#)

[Interacting with other apps](#)

[Useful tools & resources](#)

[Acknowledgements](#)

<u>Before you read on - Some brilliant alternative BlueSky guides from others</u>	
A guide created by Mark Rubin & Steve Haroz one which this one was initially inspired by	Link here
A guide on the LSE blog by Ned Potter	Link here & related guide
A guide specifically aimed at libraries, also by Ned potter	Link here

An introduction to BlueSky & how it works

Bluesky is a federated network, meaning that it is built on a decentralized framework. This removes control from a central authority and places it with the users. This also provides interoperability between platforms. Potentially, this means that users could create their own platforms (Mastodon calls these “instances”). It also means that there may be future interoperability with Mastodon.

The other benefit of a decentralized platform is that it enables users to choose from various feeds created by the developers or other users, meaning they aren't locked into an algorithm. However, this means that things work a little differently than you may be used to.

Tips

- Likes don't help to promote content, so **repost!**
 - However, custom feeds can sort content in a variety of ways so check the feed description if you have a preferred feed
- **Use hashtags** - they help specific feeds to capture your content
- **Follow feeds** of interest & create your own to really tailor your experience
- **Utilise starter packs** to get started and to find new people to follow; they're a fantastic way to smooth the transition and always find new people with shared interests
- **Follow lots of people** as the ability to create your own feeds means that to make your “following” feed interesting, you should follow many more people than you may have done so elsewhere. It's also just nice to follow people.

Finding people to follow

The best way to find people to follow is to import them from other platforms using tools like Skybridge or by utilising “starter packs”.

Find the people you were following

The easiest way to find accounts from Twitter/X is to use the Sky Follower Bridge Chrome plugin. There is a [video and text-based walkthrough](#) on how to find the accounts you followed on Twitter/X.

Find new people to follow - Starter packs

Starter packs are user-created lists of accounts to follow. These may be grouped by themes or interests. Once you've gotten started, you can create your own starter pack too! You can use these starter packs to follow everyone all at once or to browse through for individual accounts. These can also include up to 3 feeds within the starter pack.

Some useful starter packs include:

- [Preprint experts](#)
- [Open Science researchers and experts](#)
- [Metascience and open science 1](#)
- [Metascience and open science 2](#)
- [Research integrity](#)
- [Open Research library teams](#)
- [Open science folks](#)
- [Sci.com folks](#)

There are also numerous field-specific starter packs and other lists that you can browse and search using [this tool](#).

To create your own starter pack, navigate to “Profile” and then “Starter Packs”. You will be presented with a screen to give the pack a name and description. You will not be able to search and add accounts.

Feeds - follow timelines based on topics of interest

With BlueSky, you can select feeds based on specific interests, communities, or content types, offering much greater control over the algorithm's influence on what you see. To find interesting feeds, the in-built BlueSky search works well, although there are also third party apps available.

Different feeds can promote and highlight posts in different ways (effectively allowing you to choose your own “algorithm”). Some feeds are simply the latest posts/reposts sort chronologically whilst others are more algorithmic and prioritise content on likes/reposts and engagement.

To subscribe to a feed:

1. Navigate to “Feeds” & scroll down to “Discover New Feeds”
2. Enter your search term
3. Click on the plus icon next to the feed to pin the feed

You can quickly switch between pinned feeds by scrolling along the top menu bar or on the individual feeds to the right side of the screen. To locate all of your feeds, click the large “#” button or “Feeds” button.

Some useful feeds to follow for science & science communication are:

- Preprints
- Metaresearch

- Scientific Publishing
- AcademicSky
- Science
- Open Research

There's a full list of (>200) science feeds maintained by [Mark Rubin](#) available [here](#).

You can also create your own feed for personal use or to share with others using tools such as [skyfeed](#). To create your own feed:

- Check that there are no similar feeds already (<https://bsky.app/feeds>)
- Use a third party tool (such as skyfeed.app) and follow their guidance

If you want to inject some of the content from feeds you follow into your main feed you can do this in the settings:

- Settings > Content > Following Feed > Show samples of your feeds in your following feed

Lists can also be used to follow specific groups of people, rather than topics as with feeds, or they can be used to quickly block a wide range of people. For example, the [following list](#) searches for "MAGA" and enables you to block all of those accounts in one click.

Privacy settings

BlueSky has a range of privacy settings and features. A semi-complete list is provided below:

Protecting your posts

- disabling replies on your posts
- limiting replies on your posts to people you follow, mention, or include in specific lists
- disabling quote posting on your posts
- detaching your post from someone else's quote
- changing the above interaction settings even after a post is sent
- hiding replies to your posts for yourself or for everyone
- self-labeling your media for adult or graphic content to protect other users
- limiting account visibility only to logged in users
 - note: this is not 100% enforceable but all major bluesky clients and apps support it

Limiting your interaction

- blocking users from seeing or interacting with your posts
 - if you block after an interaction, they vaporize
 - if they've replied already, the entire thread below their reply is cauterized for everyone, floating in space detached from your post
 - note: your blocks are publicly visible via 3rd party apps
- muting users to remove them from your notis and feeds, and hide them in replies
 - note: your mutes are private
- muting or blocking entire moderation lists of users
 - note: inclusion in a list is public via third party apps. muting a list is private, blocks via a list are public
- subscribing to other people's mod lists
 - note: your subscription is private, muting & blocking work the same
- subscribing to labelers (moderation services) from bluesky or third parties
 - decide whether to show, warn, or hide posts that have been labeled in each category
 - report content that should be labeled to bluesky and/or third parties labelers

One unique feature is the ability to detach your original posts from quote posts. This helps to limit yourself from being “piled-on” as easily.

Interacting with other apps & account security

BlueSky creates individual passwords to login to other apps and services. This helps keep your account more secure. To generate an app password, navigate to your settings (1) and then Privacy & Security - App Passwords (2). (Whilst you're here, you should turn on 2FA for extra security). On the next screen, select Add app password.

Useful tools & resources

<https://www.sky-follower-bridge.dev/get-started.html> - Find and quickly follow people who have Twitter/X accounts.

<https://blueskydirectory.com/starter-packs/all> - To find starter packs and other tools

<https://skyfeed.app/> - create personal views and create feeds

<https://goodfeeds.co/> - To find existing feeds

 BlueSky for Scientists - A guide created by [Mark Rubin](#) & [Steve Haroz](#)

 BlueSky Science-Related Feeds - full list of (>200) science feeds maintained by [Mark Rubin](#)

<https://github.com/fishttp/awesome-bluesky> - Fantastic list of tools for BlueSky

<https://docs.bsky.app/showcase> - BlueSky curated list of tools and community projects

[Buffer](#) or [Publer](#) - for scheduling posts and cross-posting to different platforms

Acknowledgements

A huge shout out needs to go to Mark Rubin, whose incredibly helpful posts aided me in getting started. He is also maintaining some excellent resources for scientists, including a getting started guide and a list of over 200 science related feeds.